

Heterocyclic Compounds from β -Diketones. Part I. Sulphanilamidobenzeneazoacetates and their Cyclisation

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2-Sulphanilamidobenzeneazoacetates have been obtained by interaction of sulphanilamidobenzene diazonium chlorides and ethyl acetoacetate. Their behaviours with hydrazine, semicarbazide, and hydroxylamine have been studied and cyclic compounds, such as, pyrazolones and isoxazolone derivatives, prepared.

2-Sulphanilamidobenzene diazonium chlorides, obtained from 2-sulphanilamidobenzenes on diazotisation, readily couple with diaminobenzenes and diaminopyridines, yielding well-known antibacterials^{1,2}. It has now been observed that 2-sulphanilamidobenzenes also couple with reactive methylene compounds, such as, ethyl acetoacetate, to form 2-sulphanilamidobenzeneazoacetates.

These compounds react, like other β -keto-esters, with hydrazine hydrate, semicarbazide acetate, phenylhydrazine, and hydroxylamine acetate to form pyrazolones, pyrazolone-amides, phenylpyrazolones, and isoxazolone derivatives. Thus, 2-sulphanilamidobenzeneazoacetate (I) with hydrazine hydrate in acetic acid yields 3-methyl-4-(2'-sulphanilamidobenzeneazo)-5-pyrazolone (II); with semicarbazide acetate in ethanol, 3-methyl-4-(2'-sulphanilamidobenzeneazo)-5-pyrazolone-1-amide (III); with phenylhydrazine in acetic acid, 1-phenyl-3-methyl-4-(2'-sulphanilamidobenzeneazo)-5-pyrazolone (IV); with hydroxylamine acetate in ethanol, 3-methyl-4-(2'-sulphanilamidobenzeneazo)-5-isoxazolone (V). The isoxazolone (V), when heated with phenylhydrazine in acetic acid, is converted into the phenylpyrazolone derivative (IV). The structure of (IV) also follows from its formation from ethyl acetoacetate when it is first treated with phenylhydrazine and then coupling the product formed (VI) with 2-sulphanilamidobenzene diazonium chloride.

1. Mangini, *Boll. sci. facolta chim. ind., Bologna*, 1940, No. 4, 127; Marques, *Bol. soc. quim., Peru*, 1940, No. 1, 19.

2. Riesz *et al.*, *Congr. Intern. Biochim., Resumés Communs.*, 3rd Congr., Brussels, 1958, p. 91.

EXPERIMENTAL

2-Sulphanilamidobenzeneazoacetate (I).—A diazotised solution of 2-sulphanilamidobenzene (2.4 g.) was poured on a cooled mixture of sodium acetate (100 g.), ethyl acetoacetate (1.3 g.), water (25 ml), and ethanol (25 ml) and shaken vigorously. A pale yellow precipitate separated which on recrystallisation from ethanol afforded 80% yield of 2-sulphanilamidobenzeneazoacetate in golden yellow needles, m.p. 165°. (Found: S, 8.19. $C_{18}H_{16}O_3N_3S$ requires S, 8.22%).

2,4-DNP of compound (I) was obtained as orange-red plates, m.p. 219°. (Found: S, 5.53. $C_{24}H_{24}O_8N_3S$ requires S, 5.61%).

By adopting a similar procedure a few more 2-sulphanilamidobenzeneazoacetates have been prepared and are reported in Table I.

TABLE I

Substituted sulphanilamidobenzeneazoacetates.

Compounds.	M.P.	Colour.	Yield.	% Sulphur.		2,4-DNP.	
				Found.	Reqd.	M.P.	Colour.
-2-Chloro-	119°	Light yellow	78%	7.48	7.55	108°	Orange
-3-Chloro-	160°	Dark "	70	7.49	7.55	185°	"
-4-Chloro-	160°	Yellow	76	7.49	7.55	200°	Orange-red
-2-Methyl-	114°	Lemmon "	80	7.83	7.94	220°	Red
-3-Methyl-	143°	Yellow	78	7.83	7.94	200°	Reddish yellow
-4-Methyl-	149°	Dull "	78	7.85	7.94	180°	Orange-yellow
-2-Methoxy-	140°	Yellow	83	7.57	7.63	205°	Orange-red
-4-Methoxy-	165°	"	82	7.59	7.63	215°	"
-2-Ethoxy-	109°	Lemmon "	83	7.28	7.39	185°	"
-4-Ethoxy-	129°	Dull "	83	7.29	7.39	100°	Orange

3-Methyl-4-(2'-sulphanilamidobenzeneazo)-5-pyrazolone (II).—A solution of compound (I) (3.8 g.) in glacial acetic acid (10 ml) and hydrazine hydrate (1 g.) were heated for 2 hours. On cooling and adding water, a yellow precipitate separated which on recrystallisation from ethanol furnished 75% of 3-methyl-4-(2'-sulphanilamidobenzeneazo)-5-pyrazolone in yellow needles, m.p. 158°. (Found: S, 8.90. $C_{16}H_{14}O_3N_3S$ requires S, 8.96%).

By adopting a similar procedure, a few 3-methyl-4-(2'-sulphanilamidobenzeneazo)-5-pyrazolones have been prepared and are recorded in Table II.

3-Methyl-4-(2'-sulphanilamidobenzeneazo)-5-pyrazolone-1-amide (III).—A solution of compound (I) (3.8 g.) in ethanol (10 ml), semicarbazide hydrochloride (1 g.), and sodium acetate (0.5 g.) were refluxed for 2 hours. On adding water, a precipitate separated which on recrystallisation from ethanol provided 76% of 3-methyl-4-(2'-sulphanilamidobenzeneazo)-5-pyrazolone-1-amide in yellow flakes, m.p. 228°. (Found: S, 7.91. $C_{17}H_{16}O_4N_3S$ requires S, 8.00%).

It formed a silver salt with ammoniacal silver nitrate solution which with HCl and NH_4OH furnished 3-methyl-4-(2'-sulphanilamidobenzeneazo)-5-pyrazolone (II), m.p. 158°.

By adopting a similar procedure, a few 3-methyl-4-(2'-sulphanilamidobenzeneazo)-5-pyrazolone-1-amides have been prepared and are recorded in Table III.

TABLE II
Substituted pyrazolones from azo-esters.

*Azo-esters No.	M.P.	Colour.	Yield.	% Sulphur.	
				Found.	Reqd.
1	157°	Yellow	70%	8.10	8.17
2	190°	Dirty yellow	70	8.10	8.17
3	193°	Lemmon "	72	8.09	8.17
4	100°	" "	72	8.54	8.62
5	192°	Yellow	70	8.66	8.62
6	201°	Pale "	71	8.66	8.62
7	196°	Yellow	68	8.17	8.26
8	207°	Dirty "	71	8.18	8.26
9	163°	Pale "	71	7.85	7.98
10	189°	" "	70	7.89	7.98

*As recorded in Table I.

TABLE III
Substituted pyrazolone-1-amides from azo-esters.

*Azo-esters No.	M.P.	Colour.	Yield.	% Sulphur.	
				Found.	Reqd.
1	183°	Orange-yellow	79%	7.29	7.36
2	216°	Golden "	78	7.30	7.36
3	212°	Yellow	79	7.29	7.36
4	230°	Dirty "	73	7.65	7.72
5	204°	Golden "	73	7.64	7.72
6	203°	Golden orange	74	7.64	7.72
7	212°	Lemmon-yellow	68	7.37	7.44
8	235°	Yellow	68	7.36	7.44
9	189°	Golden "	74	7.12	7.20
10	213°	Yellow	74	7.09	7.20

* As recorded in Table I.

1-Phenyl-3-methyl-4-(2'-sulphanilamidobenzeneazo)-5-pyrazolone (IV).—A solution of compound (I) (3.8 g.) in acetic acid (10 ml) and phenylhydrazine (1 g.) were heated for 1 hour and then cooled. A solid separating was recrystallised from acetic acid to provide the product (IV) in golden orange plates, m.p. 259°. (Found: S, 7.35. $C_{22}H_{16}O_3N_2S$ requires S, 7.39%).

By a similar procedure as above, a few 1-phenyl-3-methyl-4-(2'-sulphanilamidobenzeneazo)-5-pyrazolones were prepared. These are recorded in Table IV.

TABLE IV

Substituted phenylpyrazolones from azo-esters.

*Azo-esters No.	M.P.	Colour.	Yield.	% Sulphur.	
				Found.	Reqd.
1	180°	Orange-red	76%	6.78	6.84
2	236°	" "	76	6.78	6.84
3	260°	Golden orange	78	6.79	6.84
4	194°	" "	73	7.06	7.15
5	233°	Red	74	7.07	7.15
6	240°	Orange-yellow	75	7.09	7.15
7	190°	Yellow	74	6.83	6.91
8	223°	" "	74	6.84	6.91
9	170°	Dark "	75	6.63	6.70
10	210°	Lemmon "	75	6.64	6.70

* As recorded in Table I.

3-Methyl-4-(2'-sulphanilamidobenzeneazo)-5-isoxazolone (V).—A solution of compound (I) (3.8 g.) in ethanol (10 ml), hydroxylamine hydrochloride (1 g.), and sodium acetate (0.5 g.) were refluxed for 2 hours. On adding water, a precipitate separated which on recrystallisation from acetic acid afforded 70% of the product (V) as pale yellow needles, m.p. 200°. (Found: S, 8.87. $C_{16}H_{14}O_4N_4S$ requires S, 8.93%).

A few 3-methyl-4-(2'-sulphanilamidobenzeneazo)-5-isoxazolones were prepared similarly. These are recorded in Table V.

TABLE V

Substituted isoxazolones from azo-esters.

*Azo-esters No.	M.P.	Colour.	Yield.	% Sulphur.	
				Found.	Reqd.
1	200°	Dirty yellow	65%	8.10	8.15
2	215°	Yellow	67	8.09	8.15
3	200°	Pale "	67	8.09	8.15
4	208°	Yellow	64	8.59	8.67
5	220°	Dull "	64	8.59	8.67
6	225°	Yellow	64	8.60	8.67
7	208°	" "	66	8.15	8.24
8	214°	Light "	66	8.16	8.24
9	185°	Lemmon "	67	7.87	7.96
10	192°	Yellow	67	7.89	7.96

* As recorded in Table I.

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